

CONTROLLING COPOLYMERIZATION OF 2-PYRROLIDINONE WITH E-CAPROLACTAM AND THEIR THERMAL PROPERTIES

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1 Introduction

Biodegradable natural polymer was observed at least 70 years ago and a variety of biodegradable polymers has been synthesized and researched. One of the important factors in biodegradation is existence of hydrolysable linkage such as ester, amide, urethane group in main chain. Among them, we focused on polyamide. Because it has been found that polyamide4 is susceptible to biodegradation in soil and has excellent thermal and mechanical properties based on their high melting point(260°C)[1]. Polypyrrolidone (Nylon-4) which is similar to natural cotton in terms of the hygroscopic properties, dyeability, anti-electrostatic property, and similar to Nylon-6 in terms of tensile strength and modulus was highlighted as a dream fiber in early 1970s. Moreover the monomer can be synthesized from biomass, and the polymer is biodegradable. But the most crucial problem of developing Nylon-4 compound is that the polymer lacks the presence of thermal stability. With its low thermal decomposition temperature(T_d) which is lower than melting point(mp), Nylon4 shows poor spinning processability. In case of homo compound, the ceiling temperature is known to be 80°C and because of such characteristic, to prevent unzipping in melt spinning, copolymerization of caprolactam is vital. The polypyrrolidinone(Nylon4) is obtained by anionic ring-opening polymerization of 2-pyrrolidinone and sodium or potassium salt is used as an initiator in the polymerization. And activator is essential for the initiation because the initiation without activator is very slow. We used N-acylactam and terephthaloyl-bis-lactam as an activator. The obtained polymers were analysed by FT-IR and proton NMR. Molecular weight was obtained using intrinsic viscosity and its thermal properties were measured by TGA and DSC.

2 Experimental

2.1 Material

Purification of the monomers to polymerization which are 2-pyrrolidinone (Aldrich, 99%, USA) and ε-caprolactam(Aldrich, 99%,USA) was achieved by azeotropic distillation and stored under a nitrogen atmosphere. ε-Caprolactam is difficult for use at room temperature because its melting point is 70°C. So, we mixed 2-pyrrolidinone and caprolactam to make the melting point lower. The mixture (mol ratio approximately 1:1) was liquid state at room temperature. Sodium metal was used as catalyst and benzoyl chloride (KANTO Chemical, 99%, Japan) and terephthaloyl chloride(TCI), synthesized activated monomers which were N-acyl lactam[2] (mono functional) and terephthaloyl-bis-caprolactam (di-functional)[3] were used for activators. Formic acid(SAMCHUN, 85%, Korea), m-cresol(KANTO Chemical, 98%, Japan), toluene(SAMCHUN, 99.5%, Korea)were used as received.

2.2 Synthesis of activated monomer

The mono-functional activated monomer which is N-benzoyl pyrrolidinone was synthesized according to the following methods. A mixture of 2-pyrrolidinone, pyridine and benzoyl chloride which was added into 2-neck flask under a nitrogen atmosphere was boiled under reflux for six hour. Then the mixture was cooled and poured into cool water. The N-benzoyl pyrrolidinone was collected on a glass filter and washed with water. And the powder was dried at 50°C under vacuum for 24 hours.

And, the di-functional activated monomer which is terephthaloyl-bis-caprolactam was synthesized according to the following methods. Epsilon-caprolactam was heated under a vacuum to remove

water. The decompression was continued until 1/5 of the epsilon-caprolactam was removed from the reaction flask. The epsilon-caprolactam was allowed to cool, after which purified pyridine was added. And terephthaloyl chloride was added. Then the mixture was heated to 135°C for 12 hour. After that time, the mixture was cooled and poured into cool water to precipitate the terephthaloyl-bis-caprolactam. The product was collected on a glass filter and washed with water. And the powder was dried at 50°C for 24 hours under vacuum.

2.3 Homopolymerization

2-Pyrrolidinone(10ml) was added into 2-neck flask under a nitrogen atmosphere. And sodium metal(3mol%) was added. After dissolved completely, mono-functional activated monomer which is N-benzoyl chloride was added (1.5mol%, 1mol%, 0.5mol%). Then the mixture was stirred at 50°C for 24 hours. The same reaction was conducted by using synthesized di-functional activated monomer. The obtained polymer was dissolved by formic acid and precipitated in acetone and washed with methanol. And it was dried for 24 hours at 50°C.[3]

Figure 1. polymerization of 2-pyrrolidinone.

2.3 Nylon 4,6 copolymerization

2.3 .1 Na/ benzoyl chloride system

The purified 2- pyrrolidinone and epsilon-caprolactam (2-pyrrolidinone: epsilon-caprolactam = 4 : 6 (mole ratio)) were added into 2-neck flask under a nitrogen atmosphere. And sodium metal (3 mol %) which was removed oxidized surface was added. After the sodium metal was completely dissolved, benzoyl chloride was added. Then, the mixture was stirred at 70°C for 72 hours. The same reaction was conducted at 80°C, 90°C, 100°C. The obtained polymers were dissolved by formic acid and precipitated in acetone and washed with methanol. And it was dried for 24 hours at 50°C.

Figure 2. Copolymerization of 2-pyrrolidinone with caprolactam

2.3 .2 Na/ terephthaloyl-bis-caprolactam system

The activator, terephthaloyl-bis-caprolactam was prepared from epsilon-caprolactam, pyridine, and terephthaloyl chloride. Initially, the epsilon-caprolactam was charged to a flask and heated to a temperature of 80°C. The melted epsilon-caprolactam was held in vacuum for 1 hour to remove water. The epsilon-caprolactam was then allowed to cool, after which pyridine was added. After which time terephthaloyl chloride was added to keep the pot temperature at about 90°C. The mixture was then heated to 140°C for 12 hours. Subsequently this reaction mixture was poured into deionized water and dried for 24 hours.

The copolymerization process was similar to Na/ benzoyl chloride system. The purified monomers were added into reaction flask under a nitrogen atmosphere. And sodium metal (3mole% of monomer) was added. After the sodium metal was completely dissolved, terephthaloyl-bis-caprolactam (1.5mole% of monomer) was added. Then, the mixture was stirred at 70°C for 72 hours. The same reaction was conducted at 80°C, 90°C, 100°C.

2.3 .3 K/ acetyl caprolactam system

The purified monomers were added into reaction flask under a nitrogen atmosphere. Potassium tert-butoxide (3mol%) was added, after which the mixture was held in vacuum for 1 hour to remove butanol. Then acetyl caprolactam was added as activator. Then, the mixture was stirred at 70°C for

72 hours. The same reaction was conducted at 80°C, 90°C, 100°C.

3 Result and discussion

3.1 Molecular weight

After obtained copolymer was dissolved into m-cresol, intrinsic viscosity of it was measured with capillary viscometer 525 13 Ic (Ubbelohde viscometer) at temperature of 25±0.1°C. And viscosity-average molecular weight of Nylon homopolymer was calculated using the Mark-Houwink equation. Number-average molecular weight of synthesized Nylon 46 copolymer was measured with GPC. The Mark-Houwink equation is as follows.

$$[\eta] = K(Mv)^\alpha$$

$$K = 3.98 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dl/g}, \alpha = 0.77$$

Amount of Activator	Mv	Yield(%)	$[\eta]$
1.5mol%	34400	77	1.24
1mol%	53000	44	1.73

Table. 1. Characterizations of Nylon-4 homopolymer.

As a result, the molecular weight of copolymer was 20000~ 45000g/mol, and yield of copolymer was 40~76%. The content of C4 in copolymer was 26~44% and the test shows that the higher reaction temperature, the lower content of C4 in copolymer.

System number	Reaction Temp (°C)	$[\eta]$ (dL/g)	Mn (g/mol)	MWD	Yield (%)	C4 in copolymer (%)
1*	70	0.49	21000	1.5	39.5	43.9
	80	0.65	25000	1.5	44.7	38.6
	90	1.24	45000	1.7	50.5	33.7
	100	1.21	30000	1.9	76.5	26.4
2*	70	1.50	45000	1.8	72.3	42.0
	80	1.44	45000	1.9	65.8	34.0
	90	1.03	32000	1.7	74.0	29.0
	100	1.21	36000	2.0	56.2	32.0
3*	70	0.87	29000	1.7	48.6	42.6
	80	0.88	24000	1.8	48.4	38.3
	90	1.15	26000	2.1	53.8	37.0

1- Na/ benzoyl chloride system

2- Na/ Terephthaloyl-bis-caprolactam system

3- K/ acetyl caprolactam system

Table. 2. Characterizations of Nylon-4 homopolymer.
3.2 H-NMR of Terephthaloyl-bis-caprolactam

Figure 3. H-NMR of synthesized activated monomer

H-NMR spectra of terephthaloyl-bis-caprolactam shows the peak of proton in cyclic ring at about 2~4ppm. Also, it shows the peak of proton in benzene ring at 7.55ppm. And almost of chloride site were substituted with epsilon-caprolactam because integral value of a is similar to integral of b peak. The yield was 90.5%.

3.3 H-NMR of Terephthaloyl-bis-caprolactam

H-NMR spectrum of copolymer sample that was dissolved in mixture of 1,2,2-trifluoroethanol and CDCl₃ (4:1 v/v) shows the peak of proton at about 1~3ppm. And sum of integral of a and d peak is similar to sum of integral of c and h peak. The content of C4 in copolymer was calculated by integral of b and f peak.

Figure 4. H-NMR spectra of nylon 4,6 copolymer

4. Conclusion

Nylon 46 copolymer was synthesized at 70, 80, 90, 100°C. Then number average molecular weight was

determined by GPC. Content of C4 could be obtained by FT-NMR analysis. As a result, Nylon 4 6 copolymer with 26~44% of C4 was obtained and it shows that the higher reaction temperature, the lower content of C4 in copolymer.

5. References

- [1] Norioki Kawasaki, Atsuyoshi nakayama, Naoko Yamano, Sahori Takeda, Yoshikazu Kawata, Noboru Yamamoto, Sei-ichi Aiba., National Instituted of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology., "Synthesis, thermal and mechanical properties and biodegradation of branched polyamide 4"., *Polymer* 46 (2005) 9987-9993
- [2] Robert C. O'Neill, new York, N. Y., and Roger J. Tull, Metuchen, N. J., "method of preparing lysine" *United States Patent Office*, 2,877,220 Patented Mar. 10, 1959
- [3] Ross Melvin Hedrick, Creve Coeur; James D. Gabbert, St. Louis, both of Mo., "lactam-polyol-polyacyl lactam terpolymers" *United States Patent* 4,031,164 Patented June 21, 1977
- [4] Norioki Kawasaki et al., "synthesis, thermal and mechanical properties and biodegradation of branched polyamide 4"., *Polymer* 46 (2005) 9987-9993